

A Conditional Singular Value Decomposition

Qi Deng^{1,2,3,4*}

Abstract

We propose a Conditional Singular Value Decomposition in the form of $A_{\{mn\}} = H_{\{mk\}}B_{\{kl\}}M_{\{ln\}}^*$ for given general matrices $A_{\{mn\}}$ and $B_{\{kl\}}$.

MSC: 15A04; 15A18; 15A23; 15A24

Key words: matrix decomposition; Singular Value Decomposition (SVD); Conditional SVD

Funding Source: The work was supported by Hubei University of Automotive Technology [grant number BK202209] and Hubei Provincial Bureau of Science and Technology [grant number 2023EHA018].

1. College of Artificial Intelligence, Hubei University of Automotive Technology, Shiyan, China
 2. Jack Welch College of Business & Technology, Sacred Heart University, Fairfield, CT, USA
 3. School of Accounting, Economics and Finance, University of Portsmouth, Portsmouth, UK
 4. Cofintelligence Financial Technology Ltd., Hong Kong and Shanghai, China
- *. Corresponding author: dq@huat.edu.cn; dengq@sacredheart.edu

1. Introduction

The Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) given as $A_{\{mn\}} = U_{A_{\{mm\}}} \Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} V_{A_{\{nn\}}}^*$ is unconditional. However, in financial econometrics applications, there is need to decompose the covariance matrix of one multivariate time series with that of another. To generalize, for two given matrices of $A_{\{mn\}}$ and $B_{\{kl\}}$, under certain conditions, there should exist at least one conditional decomposition that satisfies $A_{\{mn\}} = H_{\{mk\}} B_{\{kl\}} M_{\{ln\}}^*$. In searching for matrix decomposition and factorization literature [e.g., 1-5], we find no direct methodology that addresses this seemingly trivial problem. We propose a conditional decomposition based on the SVD, which we name the ‘‘Conditional Singular Value Decomposition’’ or ‘‘Conditional SVR’’ as a convenient designation.

2. Conditional Singular Value Decomposition

For $A_{\{mn\}} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ and $B_{\{kl\}} \in \mathbb{C}^{k \times l}$, both $A_{\{mn\}}$ and $B_{\{kl\}}$ have the SVD decompositions as:

$$A_{\{mn\}} = U_{A_{\{mm\}}} \Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} V_{A_{\{nn\}}}^* \quad (1a)$$

$$B_{\{kl\}} = U_{B_{\{kk\}}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}}^* \quad (1b)$$

where:

- 1) U 's and V 's are square complex unitary matrices;
- 2) Σ 's are rectangular diagonal matrices with non-negative real numbers on the diagonal.

Lemma 1: There exists a decomposition between $\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}}$ and $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$ in Equations 1a and 1b, respectively, that satisfies the following:

$$\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} = R_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} S_{\{ln\}}^* \quad (2)$$

where: $R_{\{mk\}}$ and $S_{\{ln\}}^*$ are diagonal matrices

1) When $k \geq l$, if $m, n \geq l$, and if the diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$ has non-zero real numbers on the diagonal, we have a definitely defined diagonal $D_{\{ll\}}$ in:

$$R_{\{mk\}} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{ll\}} & 0_{\{l(k-l)\}} \\ 0_{\{(m-l)l\}} & 0_{\{(m-l)(k-l)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mk\}} \quad (3a)$$

$$S_{\{ln\}}^* = [D_{\{ll\}} \quad 0_{\{l(n-l)\}}]_{\{ln\}} \quad (3b)$$

2) When $k \leq l$, if $m, n \geq k$, and if the diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$ has non-zero real numbers on the diagonal, we have a definitely defined diagonal $D_{\{kk\}}$ in:

$$R_{\{mk\}} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} \\ 0_{\{(m-k)k\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mk\}} \quad (4a)$$

$$S_{\{ln\}}^* = \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} & 0_{\{k(n-k)\}} \\ 0_{\{(l-k)k\}} & 0_{\{(l-k)(n-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{ln\}} \quad (4b)$$

Proof:

1) When $k \geq l$ and $m, n \geq l$ holds, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} &= R_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} S_{\{ln\}}^* \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{ll\}} & 0_{\{l(k-l)\}} \\ 0_{\{(m-l)l\}} & 0_{\{(m-l)(k-l)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mk\}} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} \\ 0_{\{(k-l)l\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{kl\}} [D_{\{ll\}} \quad 0_{\{l(n-l)\}}]_{\{ln\}} \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{ll\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} \\ 0_{\{(m-l)l\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{ml\}} [D_{\{ll\}} \quad 0_{\{l(n-l)\}}]_{\{ln\}} = \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{ll\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} D_{\{ll\}} & 0_{\{l(n-l)\}} \\ 0_{\{(m-l)l\}} & 0_{\{(m-l)(n-l)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mn\}} \\ \Rightarrow \Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{ll\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} D_{\{ll\}} & 0_{\{l(n-l)\}} \\ 0_{\{(m-l)l\}} & 0_{\{(m-l)(n-l)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mn\}} \end{aligned} \quad (5a)$$

The top-left $l \times l$ sub-diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}}$, or $\Sigma_{A_{\{ll\}}}$, exists and therefore:

$$\Sigma_{A_{\{ll\}}} = D_{\{ll\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} D_{\{ll\}} = D_{\{ll\}} D_{\{ll\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}} \quad (5b)$$

$$D_{\{ll\}} = \left(\Sigma_{A_{\{ll\}}} \Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}}^{-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (5c)$$

Equation 5c holds only if $\Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}}$ is inversible ($\Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}}^{-1}$ exists), therefore we prove Lemma 1 when $k \geq l$ and $m, n \geq l$, by tightening the condition that the top $l \times l$ sub-diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$, or $\Sigma_{B_{\{ll\}}}$, must have non-zero diagonal elements.

2) When $k \leq l$ and $m, n \geq k$ holds, we have:

$$\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} = R_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} S_{\{ln\}}^*$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)k\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mk\}} \begin{bmatrix} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(l-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{kl\}} \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(n-k)\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(l-k)k\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{(l-k)(n-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{ln\}} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(l-k)\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)k\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)(l-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{ml\}} \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(n-k)\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(l-k)k\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{(l-k)(n-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{ln\}} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} D_{\{kk\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(n-k)\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)k\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)(n-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mn\}} \\
\Rightarrow \Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}} &= \begin{bmatrix} D_{\{kk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} D_{\{kk\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{k(n-k)\}} \\ \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)k\}} & \mathbf{0}_{\{(m-k)(n-k)\}} \end{bmatrix}_{\{mn\}} \tag{6a}
\end{aligned}$$

The top-left $k \times k$ sub-diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}}$, or $\Sigma_{A_{\{kk\}}}$ exists and therefore:

$$\Sigma_{A_{\{kk\}}} = D_{\{kk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} D_{\{kk\}} = D_{\{kk\}} D_{\{kk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}} \tag{6b}$$

$$D_{\{kk\}} = \left(\Sigma_{A_{\{kk\}}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}}^{-1} \right)^{\frac{1}{2}} \tag{6c}$$

Equation 6c holds only if $\Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}}$ is invertible ($\Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}}^{-1}$ exists), therefore we prove Lemma 1 when $k \leq l$ and $m, n \geq k$, by tightening the condition that the left $k \times k$ sub-diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$, or $\Sigma_{B_{\{kk\}}}$, must have non-zero diagonal elements.

Theorem 1: Let $A_{\{mn\}} \in \mathbb{C}^{m \times n}$ and $B_{\{kl\}} \in \mathbb{C}^{k \times l}$, there exists at least one conditional decomposition that satisfies the following:

$$A_{\{mn\}} = H_{\{mk\}} B_{\{kl\}} M_{\{ln\}}^* \tag{7}$$

Under either of the following conditions:

Condition 1) When $k \geq l$, if $m, n \geq l$, and if the diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$ in Equation 1b has non-zero real numbers on the diagonal;

Condition 2) When $k \leq l$, if $m, n \geq k$, and if the diagonal matrix of $\Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}}$ in Equation 1b has non-zero real numbers on the diagonal.

Proof:

We first substitute the $B_{\{kl\}}$ term in Equation 7 with the RHS of Equation 1b, resulting:

$$A_{\{mn\}} = H_{\{mk\}} \left(U_{B_{\{kk\}}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}}^* \right) M_{\{ln\}}^* = \left(H_{\{mk\}} U_{B_{\{kk\}}} \right)_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} \left(M_{\{nl\}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}} \right)_{\{ln\}}^* \quad (8a)$$

We then substitute the $\Sigma_{A_{\{mn\}}}$ term in Equation 1a with the RHS of Equation 2, resulting:

$$A_{\{mn\}} = U_{A_{\{mm\}}} \left(R_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} S_{\{ln\}}^* \right) V_{A_{\{nn\}}}^* = \left(U_{A_{\{mm\}}} R_{\{mk\}} \right)_{\{mk\}} \Sigma_{B_{\{kl\}}} \left(V_{A_{\{nn\}}} S_{\{nl\}} \right)_{\{ln\}}^* \quad (8b)$$

Comparing the RHSs of Equations 8a and 8b, we get the follows:

$$\left(H_{\{mk\}} U_{B_{\{kk\}}} \right)_{\{mk\}} = \left(U_{A_{\{mm\}}} R_{\{mk\}} \right)_{\{mk\}} \quad (9a)$$

$$\left(M_{\{nl\}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}} \right)_{\{ln\}}^* = \left(V_{A_{\{nn\}}} S_{\{nl\}} \right)_{\{ln\}}^* \Rightarrow \left(M_{\{nl\}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}} \right)_{\{nl\}} = \left(V_{A_{\{nn\}}} S_{\{nl\}} \right)_{\{nl\}} \quad (9b)$$

Solving Equations 9a and 9b, we get:

$$H_{\{mk\}} = U_{A_{\{mm\}}} R_{\{mk\}} U_{B_{\{kk\}}}^* \quad (10a)$$

$$M_{\{nl\}} = V_{A_{\{nn\}}} S_{\{nl\}} V_{B_{\{ll\}}}^* \quad (10b)$$

If Condition 1 holds, we substitute $R_{\{mk\}}$ and $S_{\{nl\}}$ in Equations 10a and 10b with Equations 3a and 3b, respectively, with $D_{\{ll\}}$ given by Equation 5C. If Condition 2 holds, we substitute $R_{\{mk\}}$ and $S_{\{nl\}}$ with Equations 4a and 4b, respectively, with $D_{\{kk\}}$ given by Equation 6C. As all the matrices exist, we thus prove Theorem 1.

It is trivial to prove that both HH^* and MM^* are symmetric matrices for any permutation of m, n, k, l that satisfies the constraints in either condition. For example, from Equation 10a we get:

$$\left(H_{\{mk\}} H_{\{km\}}^* \right)^* = H_{\{mk\}} H_{\{km\}}^*$$

3. A Special Case

In case that $m = n = k = l$, Equation 7 is reduced to:

$$A = HBH^* \quad (11)$$

A and B have the SVD decomposition given as:

$$A = U_A \Sigma_A U_A^* \quad (12a)$$

$$B = U_B \Sigma_B U_B^* \quad (12b)$$

- 1) U 's are square complex unitary matrices;
- 2) Σ 's are rectangular diagonal matrices with non-negative real numbers on the diagonal.

And there exists a decomposition between Σ_A and Σ_B as:

$$\Sigma_A = R \Sigma_B R^* \quad (13)$$

where: R is a diagonal matrix with real numbers on the diagonal

$$\Rightarrow \Sigma_A = R R^* \Sigma_B = R R \Sigma_B$$

$$\Rightarrow R = (\Sigma_A \Sigma_B^{-1})^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (14)$$

By substituting Σ_A in Equation 12a with the RHS of Equation 13 we get:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= U_A (R \Sigma_B R^*) U_A^* \\ \Rightarrow A &= (U_A R) \Sigma_B (U_A R)^* \end{aligned} \quad (15a)$$

Also, substitute B in Equation 11 with the RHS of Equation 12b:

$$\begin{aligned} A &= H (U_B \Sigma_B U_B^*) H^* \\ \Rightarrow A &= (H U_B) \Sigma_B (H U_B)^* \end{aligned} \quad (15b)$$

By comparing Equation 15a and Equation 15b we get:

$$\begin{aligned} U_A R &= H U_B \\ \Rightarrow H &= U_A R U_B^* \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Equation 16 solves H in proposition $A = H B H^*$, with $H H^*$ being a symmetric matrix.

4. Discussion

In this short note we prove that there exists a Conditional SVD of $A_{\{mn\}} = H_{\{mk\}} B_{\{kl\}} M_{\{ln\}}^*$, and provide an analytical solution for it. We contribute to the literature of matrix decomposition, and especially that of the SVD, by proposing a technique that directly addresses the decomposition of $A_{\{mn\}}$ under the condition that $B_{\{kl\}}$ is also given. We also provide a special case, that when $m = n = k = l$, a reduced conditional SVD in the form of $A = H B H^*$ exists.

Declaration of competing interest

There is no competing interest.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

References

- [1] Stewart, G.W., 1993. On the early history of the singular value decomposition. *SIAM review*, 35(4), pp.551-566; doi; <https://doi.org/10.1137/1035134>.
- [2] Stewart, G.W., 1998. *Matrix algorithms: volume 1: basic decompositions*. SIAM: Society for Industrial and Applied Mathematics; 1st edition (August 1, 1998), ISBN-10: 0898714141, ISBN-13: 978-089871414 .
- [3] <https://docs.scipy.org/doc/scipy/tutorial/linalg.html>, accessed on Feb 24, 2024.
- [4] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Matrix_decomposition, accessed on Feb 24, 2024.
- [5] <https://mathworld.wolfram.com/MatrixDecomposition.html>, accessed on Feb 24, 2024.